

Short communication

Three new records of Megaspilidae (Hymenoptera, Ceraphronoidea) from Iran

Mitra Atbaei¹, Nazila Saghaei^{2&*} & Majid Fallahzadeh¹

1-Department of Entomology, Jahrom branch, Islamic Azad University, Jahrom, Iran & 2- Department of Entomology, Marvdasht branch, Islamic Azad University, Marvdasht, Iran.

*Corresponding author, E-mail: nazila_saghaei@yahoo.com

گزارش جدید سه گونه زنبور خانواده

Megaspilidae (Hymenoptera, Ceraphronoidea) از ایران

میترا اتباعی^۱، نازیلا سقایی^{۲*} و مجید فلاح زاده^۱

۱- گروه حشره‌شناسی، واحد جهرم، دانشگاه آزاد اسلامی، جهرم، ایران و ۲- گروه حشره‌شناسی، واحد مرودشت، دانشگاه آزاد اسلامی، مرودشت، ایران.

* مسئول مکاتبات، پست الکترونیکی: nazila_saghaei@yahoo.com

چکیده

در پژوهش حاضر، تعداد ۳۰ نمونه از زنبورهای خانواده Megaspilidae (Hymenoptera, Ceraphronoidea) از نقاط مختلف استان فارس به وسیله تله مالیز جمع‌آوری و شناسایی شد که سه گونه *Dendrocerus laticeps* (Hedicke, 1929)، *D. perlucidus* Alekseev, 1983 و *Conostigmus fasciatipennis* Kieffer, 1907 برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شود.

واژگان کلیدی: پارازیتوئید، تاکسونومی، پراکنش.

دریافت: ۱۳۹۶/۸/۷، پذیرش ۱۳۹۶/۱۰/۳.

Megaspilidae (Hymenoptera, Ceraphronoidea) is a small family of parasitic wasps, it contains two subfamilies with 12 genera and about 299 species worldwide (Aguilar *et al.*, 2013). The species of the family are primary parasitoids and hyperparasitoids on a wide range of insects including Hemiptera, Thysanoptera, Coleoptera, Diptera, Hymenoptera, Trichoptera, Lepidoptera, Neuroptera and Mecoptera (Johnson & Musetti, 2004; Mikó & Deans, 2009; Mikó *et al.*, 2011; Trietsch *et al.*, 2015).

The fauna of Iranian Megaspilidae is currently poorly known. Until now, only four species in two genera of Megaspilidae including *Dendrocerus aphidum* (Rondani, 1877); *D. conwentziae* Gahan, 1919; *D. carpenteri* (Curtis, 1829) and *Megaspilus dux* (Curtis, 1829) have been reported from Iran (Gonzalez *et al.*, 1978; Alekseev & Radchenko, 2001; Rakhshani *et al.*, 2005; Rezaei *et al.*, 2006; Rakhshani *et al.*, 2010; Darsoei *et al.*, 2011; Jafari & Modarres Awal, 2012).

The current study is based on specimens collected by Malaise-traps from different areas of the Fars province in southern Iran. The specimens were identified by Dr. Istvan Mikó. The

voucher specimens are deposited at the Department of Entomology, Jahrom Branch, Islamic Azad University, Jahrom, Iran (JIAU) and in the collection of the North Carolina State University, USA (NCSU).

We collected four species of two genera belonging to the subfamily Megaspilinae as follows:

***Dendrocerus aphidum* (Rondani, 1877)**

Specimens examined: 2 ♂, 7 ♀, Fars province, Khonj (27°53'31"N, 53°26'42"E), 6.iv.2013, leg. M. Atbaei; 1 ♂, same data, 20.vi.2013; 1 ♀, Fars province, Kherameh (29°30'51"N, 53°18'40"E), 13.vi.2013, leg. E. Izadi; 2 ♂, Fars province, Larestan (27°38'N, 54°16'E), 5.v.2013, leg. A. Falahatpisheh.

General distribution: Cosmopolitan (Dessart, 2001; Johnson & Musetti, 2004; Mikó *et al.*, 2011).

Remarks: The genus *Dendrocerus* Ratzeburg is a worldwide large genus including over 100 species and 37 of them are recorded from the Palaearctic region (Johnson & Musetti, 2004). Members of the genus recognized by: presence of a posterior mesotibial spur, subdivision of the metasomal synsternum, bifurcated calcar, parossiculus distolaterally separated from gonostipes, 9 female flagellomeres, pterostigma and occipital depression, absence of Waterston's organ and axillar setae (Mikó *et al.*, 2011). As far as their biology is known, the species of the genus *Dendrocerus* are commonly hyperparasitoids of aphids (Fergusson, 1980; Mikó *et al.*, 2011).

In Iran, *D. aphidum* has already been recorded as *D. breadalbimensis* (Kieffer, 1907) (Gonzalez *et al.*, 1978).

***Dendrocerus laticeps* (Hedicke, 1929)**

Specimens examined: 2 ♂, Fars province, Khonj (27°53'31"N, 53°26'42"E), 2.iii.2013, leg. M. Atbaei; 3 ♀, 4 ♂, same data, 6.iv.2013; 1 ♀, same data, 11.v.2013; 3 ♀, same data, 20.vi.2013; 1 ♂, Fars province, Kherameh (29°30'51"N, 53°18'40"E), 12.vi.2013, leg. E. Izadi

General distribution: Cosmopolitan (Dessart, 2001; Johnson & Musetti, 2004).

Remarks: In the Palaearctic region, *Dendrocerus laticeps* has previously been reported from Europe, China, Japan, Iraq (Dessart, 2001) and hereby it is a new species record for Iran.

***Dendrocerus perlucidus* Alekseev, 1983**

Specimens examined: 1 ♀, Fars province, Khonj (27°53'31"N, 53°26'42"E), 2.iii.2013, leg. M. Atbaei

General distribution: Afrotropical region (Africa, UAE) and Palaearctic region (Europe) (Dessart, 2001; Johnson & Musetti, 2004; Mikó *et al.*, 2011).

Remarks: *Dendrocerus perlucidus* is a new species record for Iran. Recently, two species *D. aphidum* and *D. perlucidus* were re-described by Mikó *et al.* (2011).

***Conostigmus fasciatipennis* Kieffer, 1907**

Specimens examined: 2 ♂, Fars province, Kherameh (29°30'51"N, 53°18'40"E), 13.vi.2013, leg. E. Izadi; 1 ♀, Fars province, Khonj (27°53'31"N, 53°26'42"E), 20.vi.2013, leg. M. Atbaei

General distribution: Palaearctic region (Europe).

Remarks: The genus *Conostigmus* includes more than 172 known species and about 97 species have been reported from the Palaearctic region (Johnson & Musetti, 2004; Bijoy *et al.*, 2014; Mikó *et al.*, 2016). A few studies have been conducted on the biology of the members of this genus. Species of the genus have been reared from puparia of Syrphidae and eggs and larvae of Cecidomyiidae (Trietsch *et al.*, 2015). Members of the genus are recognized by the following characters: mesonotum roundish anteriorly and constricted toward the head; parapsidal grooves curved smoothly toward the anterior angles of the mesonotum, segments of the antennal funicle of males cylindrical, forms usually with rudimentary or reduced wings (Alekseev, 1987). Here, *Conostigmus fasciatipennis* is a new species record for Iran.

Acknowledgements

We are most grateful to Dr. Istvan Mikó (Insect Museum, Department of Entomology, North Carolina State University, USA) for the identification of the specimens.

References

- Alekseev, Y.N.** (1987) Superfamily Ceraphronoidea (Ceraphronids). pp 1213–1257 in Medvedev, G.S., (Ed). *Keys to the insects of the European part of the USSR*, vol. III, part 2. 1341 pp. Amerind, New Delhi, India.
- Alekseev, V. N., & Radchenko, T. D.** (2001) Ceraphronoid wasps (Hymenoptera, Ceraphronoidea) of the fauna of the Ukraine. Communication 1. *Vestnik Zoologii*, 35(3): 3–16.
- Aguiar, A., Deans, A., Engel, M., Forshage, M., Huber, J., Jennings, J., Johnson, N., Lelej, A., Longino, J., Lohrman, V., Mikó, I., Ohl, M., Ramusen, C., Taeger, A. and Ki Yu, D.** (2013) Order Hymenoptera, pp. 51–62 in: Zhang, Z.Q. (Ed.), *Animal Biodiversity: An Outline of Higher-level Classification and Survey of Taxonomic Richness*, Addenda. *Zootaxa*, 3703: 1– 82.
- Bijoy, M. C., Rajmohana, K., & Kumar, R.** (2014) First report of the genus *Conostigmus* Dahlbom (Hymenoptera: Ceraphronoidea: Megaspilidae) from India with description of a new species. *Biodiversity Data Journal* 2, e991, 1-14.
- Darsoei, R., Karimi, J., & Modarres Awal, M.** (2011) Parasitic wasps as natural enemies of aphid population in the Mashhad region of Iran: new data from DNA sequences and SEM. *Archives of Biological Sciences*, 63 (4), 1225–1234.

-
- Dessart, P.** (2001) Les Megaspilinae ni européens, ni américains. 2. Les *Dendrocerus* Ratzeburg, 1852, à mâles non flabellicornés (Hymenoptera Ceraphronoidea Megaspilidae). *Belgian Journal of Entomology*, 3: 3–124.
- Fergusson, N.** (1980) A revision of the British species of *Dendrocerus* Ratzeburg (Hymenoptera: Ceraphronoidea) with a review of their biology as aphid hyperparasites. *Bulletin of the British Museum (Natural History) Entomology*, 41, 255–314.
- Jafari, N., & Modarres Awal, M.** (2012) Aphid parasitoids associations on stone fruit trees in Khorasan Razavi Province (Iran) (Hymenoptera: Braconidae: Aphidiinae). *Munis Entomology and Zoology*, 7(1), 418–423.
- Johnson, N.F. & Musetti, L.** (2004) Catalog of the systematic literature of the superfamily Ceraphronoidea (Hymenoptera). *Contributions of the American Entomological Institute*, 33 (2), 1–149
- Gonzalez, D., White, W., Hall, J., & Dickson, R. C.** (1978) Geographical distribution of Aphidiidae [Hym.] imported to California for biological control of *Acyrtosiphon kondoi* and *Acyrtosiphon pisum* [Hom.: Aphididae]. *Entomophaga*, 23(3), 239–248.
- Mikó, I., & Deans, A. R.** (2009) *Masner*, a new genus of Ceraphronidae (Hymenoptera, Ceraphronoidea) described. *Advances in the Systematics of Hymenoptera.: Festschrift in honour of Lubomír Masner. ZooKeys*, 20, 127–153.
- Mikó, I., Yoder, M., & Deans, A.** (2011) Order Hymenoptera, family Megaspilidae Genus *Dendrocerus*. pp. 353–374 in van Harten, A. (Ed.). *Arthropod Fauna of the UAE*, vol.4, 832 pp. Dar Al Ummah Printing, Abu Dabi.
- Mikó, I., Trietsch, C., Sandall, E. L., Yoder, M. J., Hines, H., & Deans, A. R.** (2016) Malagasy *Conostigmus* (Hymenoptera: Ceraphronoidea) and the secret of scutes. *PeerJ*, 4, e2682, 1–87
- Rakhshani, E., Talebi, A., Stary, P., Manzari, S., & Rezwani, A.** (2005) Re-description and Biocontrol Information of *Pauesia antennata* (Mukerji) (Hym., Braconidae, Aphidiinae), Parasitoid of *Pterochloroides persicae* (Chol.) (Hom., Aphidoidea, Lachnidae). *Journal of the Entomological Research Society*, 7(3), 59–69.
- Rakhshani, H., Ebadi, R., Hatami, B., Rakhshani, E., & Gharali, B.** (2010) A survey of alfalfa aphids and their natural enemies in Isfahan, Iran, and the effect of alfalfa strip-harvesting on their populations. *Journal of Entomological Society of Iran*, 30(1), 13–28.
- Rezaei, N., Mossadegh, M.S. & Hodjat, H.** (2006) Aphids and their natural enemies in wheat and barley fields in Khuzestan. *The Scientific Journal of Agriculture*, 29 (2), 127–137.
- Trietsch, C., Deans, A. R., & Mikó, I.** (2015) Redescription of *Conostigmus albovarius* Dodd, 1915 (Hymenoptera, Megaspilidae), a metallic ceraphronoid, with the first description of males. *Journal of Hymenoptera Research*, 46, 137–150.
-